

A Gap Analysis between the Expectation of Industry 4.0 and the Ability of the Current Industrial Engineering Graduates in Khon Kaen University

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Abstract

Thailand has entered Industry 4.0 era, which is the recent trend in automation and data exchange in organization. The digital transformation of manufacturing processes based on intelligent machines and devices is crucial in manufacturing industries. To be an effective industry 4.0, it requires cooperation between various sectors and higher education sector is one of those. For engineering department, especially Industrial Engineering, the curriculum must be improved to conform the industrial sector requirements. Therefore, the purpose of this research is to find a gap between the qualifications of graduate students that the industry needs and the abilities of the current graduate students from Industrial engineering, Khon Kaen University. Gap analysis was used to determine the skills that the graduate students need to improve. The result shows that the current graduate students still need to improve in the skills of systematic thinking and understanding of processes related to Industry 4.0, automation technology and the big data analysis.

Keywords: Industrial Engineering Curriculum; Gap Analysis; Industry 4.0.

1 Introduction

Industry 4.0 refers to a new phase in the industrial revolution that focuses on big data, automation, machine learning, and real-time data. It also referred as internet of things (IoT) or smart manufacturing, marries physical production and operations with smart digital technology, machine learning, and big data to create a more holistic and better connected ecosystem for companies that focus on manufacturing and supply chain management. Thailand 4.0 economic model was launched by the government in May 2016. This policy is expected to complement the 12th National Economic and Social Development Plan, for 2017-2021, and support the government's new 20-year National Strategy. Thai government had set out three objectives for the Thailand 4.0 strategy: to elevate Thailand to the high-income nation status; to reduce inequality; and to promote environmentally sustainable growth and development (Wittayasin, 2017). Thailand 4.0 has the potential to leads many Thai businesses into the digital age. While several Thai organizations are already on their way to digital transformation, the challenge will be shifting the entire economic focus of the nation together with its people towards the full potential of the digital world.

To be an effective industry 4.0, it requires cooperation between various sectors, and higher industrial engineering education sector is one of those. Industrial engineers use principles of engineering, mass production and technology to help companies find the ways to offer service or create a product efficiently. This requires knowledge of economics, workplace safety standards and industrial practices (Kádárová, Kováč, Durkáčová, & Kádár, 2014) and the industrial engineer, who obtained higher-level degree, plays a decisive role as transmitter or introducer of progress. The balanced combination of a solid scientific and technical education, different applied technologies and disciplines within the economic-business and social-humanistic areas, the understanding that comes from the reality of the industrial sector and the ability to interrelate various disciplines involved in complex systems, makes these studies a current and innovative model. Industry 4.0 took up a pioneering role in industrial IT, which is currently revolutionizing the manufacturing engineering (Coşkun, Kayıkcı, and Gençay, 2019). Many industrialized countries had already adapted their industrial infrastructure to meet the requirements of the Industry 4.0 vision. An important task in the preparation for Industry 4.0 is the adaption of the higher education, in particular the industrial engineering education, to fulfil the requirements

of this vision. The Industry 4.0 concepts are implemented with a content of curricula into existing courses and new study modules are designed for the engineering education.

Khon Kaen University (KKU) is a public research university in Thailand. It is the first university established in north-eastern region of Thailand and remains the oldest and largest university in the region up to this day. The university is a hub of education for north-eastern Thailand and widely recognized in Asia. The Industrial Engineering (IE) department of KKU focuses on equipping the students with knowledge, process and technology involving the industrial engineering occupations. The course offers the content of manufacturing engineering and the engineering management. The computer-aided system such as CAD, CAM and CIM are emphasized. Ideas on design and production tools are also scrutinized. However, the industrial engineering curriculum must be improved to conform the industrial sector requirements. Thus, the purpose of this research is finding a gap between the qualifications of graduate student that the industry needs and the ability of the current graduate student from Industrial Engineering department of Khon Kaen University (refer as graduate IEKKU students). We use the gap analysis to determine the skills that the graduate IEKKU students need to improve.

2 Literature reviews

In this section, a brief literature review on the influence of Industry 4.0 on higher education and gap analysis applications are provided.

There are several previous studies on the relevant of industry 4.0 and higher education institute. The importance of industry 4.0 in education had demonstrated with statistical data by Baygin et al. (2016), the data confirmed that it is necessary to train and prepare the qualified employees for the company. The rise of digital technology makes disruptive innovation, which is a huge change in industrial world. Alternative communication completely transforms the working platform and industrial production. New skills, new learning and training concepts, up-to-date and flexibility curriculum are necessary in educational system. Industry 4.0 readiness in education sector needs a strong partnership between industry and academic for human resources improvement (Ciolacu et al., 2017). Azmi et al. (2018) studied the non-technical skills required by employers in Industry 4.0 based on previous researches by using meta-analysis technique as well as interviewing employers to clarify the meta-analysis results. The results revealed that communication skills especially in English language, teamwork skills, critical thinking skills, problem-solving skills, entrepreneur skills and computer skills are essential. Higher education institution should train their students with plenty interdisciplinary teaching, research, innovation, and valuable industrial training to reach current industries' needs. Given the rise of changes in industry requirements, the education system now focused on training their students as the Engineer of Future. Aleyeva et al. (2020) applied qualitative data analysis and showed the need of soft skills development for the engineering education under the influence of the Industry 4.0 as follows: (i) IT skills, which is the role of ownership of information technologies (ii) Working with information skills, which comprises searching for information, assessing the quality and reliability of information sources, as well as the ability to effectively use the information received and share it (iii) Teamwork skills, which is the role of an interdisciplinary approach to problem solving, which refers to the possession of professional interaction and teamwork skills (iv) Flexibility, adaptability and learning. The high speed of transformations will lead to the need to retrain and change the profession, which implies that the role of self-development skills increases based on the principles of lifelong learning (v) Cognitive skills. The development of the above skills is impossible without the development of the cognitive sphere, including reflection, meta cognition and critical thinking.

Higher education institutions are now more interested in the decision-making tools development that enable them to evaluate the industry expectations and perceptions of engineering graduates' skill with the purpose of attracting and keeping them satisfied. Ramadi et al. (2016) applied gap analysis to explore the gaps between industry expectations and perceptions of engineering graduates' skill sets in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region. Importance and satisfaction levels were used to calculate skill gaps for each skill. Results revealed the skills that graduates needed most improvement were communication, time management, and continuous learning. Pimentel et al. (2016) demonstrated a gap analysis amongst employers and engineering against non-engineering students to identify the main gaps between competencies provided by the traditional

education system and the missing competencies valued by the labour market. Results showed that the employers expect higher level of personal competencies than the level that students thought they have. Furthermore, Patacsil and Tablatin (2017) presented the skills gap methodology that utilized the respondent experiences in the internship program to measure the importance of the Information Technology (IT) skills gap as perceived by IT students and the industry. The questionnaires were formulated, modified, validated and tested. Respondents of the study were the IT students enrolled in internship while industry partner respondents were the internship supervisors of the IT students. In this case the internship IT students were chosen because of they have a strong background on the company requirements based on their experience which confirm that teamwork and communication skills are highly crucial soft skills. However, there was a big range of conflict on the hard skills since IT students understood that hard skills were very important while industry understood that hard skills were somehow important. Thus, education institute should promote the soft skills and hard skills component into the curriculum. There are widely successful studies implementing gap analysis tool to find the gap skills amongst expectations of industry and higher education students' potential under Industry 4.0 era.

3 Methodology

This study is a quantitative research and questionnaire-based survey in finding the gap between the qualifications of graduate student that the industry needs and the ability of current graduate IEKKU students.

3.1 Population and Samples

This research collected the data from two population groups and analyzed the gap between the data from those two groups. The first population group was the top 100 industrial factories in Thailand that hired the graduated IEKKU students. The sample size of the first group was equal to 50, calculated from Yamane formula with 90 percent confidence interval. The stratified random sampling methods was used to find the sampling proportion of factories located in each region of Thailand as follows: central region 19 factories, North region 8 factories, Northeastern Region 9 factories, East Region 7 factories, South region 5 factories and West region 2, totaling 50 factories. The second population group was the graduate students who are currently study in Industrial Engineering, KKU. The sample size of this group was 45 since there were 80 graduate students at the research period.

3.2 Data Collection and the Interpretation of Data

This research used a questionnaire for data collection. The questionnaire details for the factories were about the expectation skills of the graduate student from the Industrial engineering under Thailand Industry 4.0 policy. The questionnaire details for the students, who were currently study at Industrial engineering, KKU, were about their current ability in each skill.

There are 10 skills considered in this research as shown in the Table 1.

Table 1. The considered skills of the graduate student from the Industrial engineering under Thailand Industry 4.0 policy

No.	Skills
1	have a systematic thinking and understanding of processes related to Industry 4.0
2	have knowledge of research and development to operate in accordance with the framework of Industry 4.0
3	be able to implement the Industry 4.0 strategy in the operations
4	capable of automation technology related to Industry 4.0
5	be able to analyze big data and evaluate data in real time
6	be able to use cloud technologies as scalable IT
7	be able to apply mobile end devices for in the operations to Industry 4.0
8	have knowledge in smart logistics to operate in the framework of Industry 4.0
9	have knowledge in sensor or relevant equipment for practice in the framework of Industry 4.0
10	have knowledge of smart service to operate in the framework of Industry 4.0

The respondents from both groups could answer the question by rating a score of 1-5 for each question, where 1 means the lowest level and 5 means the highest level. The range of the answers is equal to 5 - 1 or equal 4, and the distance of the criteria used to define the perceived level score range at each level is 4/5 or 0.80. Therefore, the average score range for data level interpretation can be specified as follows:

The lowest level has average score collected from the questionnaire between 1.00 - 1.80. Between 1.81 - 2.60 for low level, between 2.61 - 3.40 for middle level, between 3.41 - 4.20, for a high level, and between 4.21 - 5.00 for the highest level.

Then, the gap analysis can be done by considering the difference between the average scores from the first sample group and the second sample group.

4 Results

4.1 Quantitative Survey Result

The 50 factories or employers were asked to rate the expectation skills of graduate students from Industrial Engineering under Thailand Industry 4.0 policy according to each skill aspect via 10 questions. The 45 graduate IEKKU students were asked to rate their ability using the same 10 questions. The average scores of each skill from both sample groups were shown in Table 2.

Table 2. The average scores from the factories and current students of Industrial Engineering, Khon Kaen University.

No.	Skills	Factories		Students	
		Avg. Score	Level	Avg. Score	Level
1	have a systematic thinking and understanding of processes related to Industry 4.0	4.31	highest	3.98	high
2	have knowledge of research and development to operate in accordance with the framework of Industry 4.0	4.18	high	4.02	high
3	be able to implement the Industry 4.0 strategy in the operations	4.16	high	4.04	high
4	capable of automation technology related to Industry 4.0	4.42	highest	4.02	high
5	be able to analyze big data and evaluate data in real time	4.36	highest	3.89	high
6	be able to use cloud technologies as scalable IT	4.02	high	3.82	high
7	be able to apply mobile end devices for in the operations to Industry 4.0	3.96	high	3.78	high
8	have knowledge in smart logistics to operate in the framework of Industry 4.0	4.20	highest	4.24	high
9	have knowledge in sensor or relevant equipment for practice in the framework of Industry 4.0	4.11	high	3.96	high
10	have knowledge of smart service to operate in the framework of Industry 4.0	4.02	high	3.87	high

The results from Table 2. show that the factories or employers expect students to have all skills at least in the range of high level or above. The highest-level skills are the Industry 4.0 related automation technology, big data analyzing and real time data evaluation, having a systematic thinking and understanding of processes related to Industry 4.0.

4.2 Gap Analysis

The difference among the average scores from the factories and the students is shown in the last column of Table 3.

Table 3. the difference between the average scores of the factories' expectations and the current abilities of Industrial Engineering students, Khon Kaen University.

No.	Skills	Factories	Student	Diff
1	have a systematic thinking and understanding of processes related to Industry 4.0	4.31	3.98	0.33
2	have knowledge of research and development to operate in accordance with the framework of Industry 4.0	4.18	4.02	0.16
3	be able to implement the Industry 4.0 strategy in the operations	4.16	4.04	0.12
4	capable of automation technology related to Industry 4.0	4.42	4.02	0.40
5	be able to analyze big data and evaluate data in real time	4.36	3.89	0.47
6	be able to use cloud technologies as scalable IT	4.02	3.82	0.20
7	be able to apply mobile end devices for in the operations to Industry 4.0	3.96	3.78	0.18
8	have knowledge in smart logistics to operate in the framework of Industry 4.0	4.20	4.24	-0.04
9	have knowledge in sensor or relevant equipment for practice in the framework of Industry 4.0	4.11	3.96	0.15
10	have knowledge of smart service to operate in the framework of Industry 4.0	4.02	3.87	0.15

The results show that the most different average scores are the skill of being able to analyze big data and evaluate data in real time. Having a systematic thinking and understanding of processes related to Industry 4.0 was the second and the third different average scores was capability of automation technology related to Industry 4.0. The line graph of the average scores from factories and students were shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Image of a gap between expectation of Industry 4.0 and the abilities of the current Industrial Engineering Graduates in Khon Kaen University.

It can be seen that the graduate IEKKU students still need to improve the skills in term of systematic thinking and understanding of processes related to Industry 4.0, automation technology and the big data analysis.

5 Conclusion and Discussion

Many industrialized countries already started to adapt their industrial infrastructure to meet the requirements of the Industry 4.0 vision. It is an important task for the higher education sector to adapt and fulfil the requirements of the Industry 4.0 concepts. The gap between the qualifications of current graduate students and the industry needs is highly important issue for industrial engineering program. Therefore, the aim of this research is to find a gap between the qualifications of graduate students that the industry needs and the ability of the current graduate IEKKU students. By using the same set of question, factories and graduate students

were asked to rate the expectation and current skills. The Gap analysis results show that there are three skills which have the highest gap as follows: 1) a systematic thinking 2) automation technology and 3) big data analysis and real-time data evaluation.

From the industry 4.0 vision, graduate student is expected to be the researcher who can analyse big data and use that data to improve the industry further. However, from the Gap analysis results, the research and development skill considered to be only a high-level skill, due to Thailand industry environment that does not support researching and still depend on foreign technology.

In future studies, we aim to conduct a large-scale analysis which include both undergraduate and graduate students.

6 References

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